

NONVERBAL FORM OF THE LANGUAGE-EYE CONTACT

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Abstract. Since there are no verbal symbols in the situation of silence, then the intonation marker is single and is only a contextual substitute for the actual speech verb of the sound action. Emotional state markers indicate silence causators, as well as their concretizers. The kinesic somatic is represented by the following reactions of the subject of silence: eye contact, no eye contact, face, mouth, head movements, hands, posture.

Keywords: causator, zero speech act, intonation marker, non-verbal discourse, emotional state marker, somatics.

INTRODUCTION

Many linguists have written about the inseparable connection between verbal and non-verbal means in the process of speech communication. Among the non-verbal means of communication, scientists include paralinguistic (intonation, pause, breathing, diction, tempo, loudness, rhythm, tonality, melody), extralinguistic (knocking on the door, laughter, crying, various noises, etc.), kinesic (gestures, facial expressions, eye contact), proxemic (poses, body movements, distance), that is, the spatio-temporal organization of communication [6, p. 18].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

V.V. Bogdanov includes silence, which can be communicatively significant and communicatively insignificant, as part of the “non-verbal components” of verbal communication. Communicatively insignificant silence is “one of the types of a person’s physiological state” [1, p. 21], for example, when a person sleeps, works or walks alone in the park. We are interested in communicatively significant

silence, "which is interpreted as a zero speech act" [2, p. 22]. V.V. Bogdanov distinguishes 3 types of communicatively meaningful silence:

1) "silence of the addressee", silence during the change of communicative roles, it has a role-marking function;

2) "silence of the speaker", that is, silence as a zero substitute for verbal reaction; this silence is multi-valued and has an informational function;

3) silence is an ellipsis, that is, non-pronunciation (omission) of a syntagmatically redundant component, it has a syntactic-constructive function [1, p. 22–23].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kinetic somatics are represented by facial expressions, gestures, postures: eye contact, no eye contact, face, mouth, head movements, hands, posture.

1) "Eye contact" is represented by the forms of visual action verbs (look, look, stare) and a special form of the visual action verb (looking, glancing). For example: "They were silent, furtively glancing at each other" (V. Rasputin. Meeting). With the help of the kinesic somatic reaction "eye contact", the communicants either express their feelings and moods (stared anxiously, looked evilly), or try to find out the feelings of the interlocutor, because in the eyes, as in a mirror of the soul, much can be seen. Silence in such cases expresses expectation, the choice by the subjects of silence of the correct tactics of behavior in their opinion.

2) The kinesic somatic "lack of eye contact" is manifested by the following linguistic means:

a) an imperfective visual action verb (IVA) and its forms (looked, looked, looking). For example: "Pavel sat, was silent, looking at the floor with heavy thought..." (V. Rasputin. Farewell to Matera). In this and other examples, the subjects of silence are in a state of contemplation and are motionless looking "at the floor", "at the sky", "at the tip of a cigarette", "out the window", "at the fire", "somewhere in the corner", "into the wall", "somewhere through". All objects of

visual action are static, allow you to escape from the outside world and completely indulge in reflection;

b) the form of the verb of visual action of the perfect form (VA) (looking), for example: “There is silence in which the guy restlessly turns his head, looking first at the old woman, then at the old man” (V. Rasputin. Money for Mary) . One of the subjects of silence is in a state of anxiety: he turns his head, his gaze moves from one object to another. He does not understand what is happening around; c) verbs of visual action and their IVA forms (examine, observe). In the examples of this subgroup, the subjects of silence focus their gaze on random objects (foreign objects, buttons, toe of a shoe). In addition, their gaze is focused and attentive. This is related to the causator of silence: waiting in an awkward, uncomfortable situation. Thus, the kinesic somatic “lack of eye contact” occurs in a situation of silence, when the subject of silence is in a state of contemplation, anxiety, or waiting in an awkward situation. We labeled this group as "no eye contact" because the communicants do not look each other, their eyes are directed to another object.

3) The kinesic somatic “face” is expressed by the verbs “frown”, “frown”, for example: “Egor Severyanych frowned displeasably, lit a cigarette. He was silent for a long time ”(V. Shukshin. Stepkina love). When the subject of silence frowns, he is in a state of heavy contemplation. This kinesic somatic can be expressed in the form of the verb “throw up”, for example: “Andrei was surprised, kept silent expectantly, raised his eyebrows, - whether they are serious, but agreed to the graves” (V. Rasputin. Farewell to Matera). In this example, the upward movement of the eyebrows characterizes the state of surprise. The author points to the protagonist's expectant silence, but non-verbal discourse contains an additional meaning of silence: the subject is not only in a state of expectation, but also of surprise.

4) The kinesic somatic “mouth” combines the actions performed by the mouth and lips. They are represented by the following linguistic means:

a) the verb “smile”, for example: “He was silent, smiled stupidly and could not look into the eyes of either his mother or his daughter” (V. Shukshin. Lenka). The communicant is in a situation of confusion, he does not know what to do;

b) the verb of a single action “spit”, for example: “Uncle also spat on the road and fell silent” (V. Shukshin. Nephew of the chief accountant). The action performed by the subject of silence speaks of his dissatisfaction, and also characterizes the state of reflection. Spitting, the subject seems to pass from one thought to another;

c) the form of the long action verb “to suck”, when the subject of silence is in a state of contemplation, while he performs mechanical monotonous actions.

5) The kinesic somatic “head movement” is expressed by the following linguistic means:

a) with the verb VA “to turn away”, for example: “Do you know what a lucky one is? “Father turned away to the river and was silent for a long time - he was offended” (V. Shukshin. Ignakha arrived). The communicant turns away because he is offended and does not want to speak;

b) with the verb of a long repeated action IVA “to pump”, when the subject of silence is dissatisfied, however, head movements indicate his reflection, the presence of an internal dialogue;

c) with the verb IVA “twirl”, for example: “There is silence, in which the guy restlessly turns his head ...” (V. Rasputin. Money for Mary). One of the subjects of silence is in a state of anxiety, he does not understand what is happening, in the process of silence he tries to understand the situation and the interlocutors.

6) The kinesic somatic “hands” is expressed by the following linguistic means:

a) verbal combinations “put her palms on her forehead”, “putting her head on her hands”, “clasping her arms around herself”. In a situation of clasping

oneself with arms, contact of hands and head, head movements down, the subject of silence is in a state of contemplation;

b) verb combinations "lowering hands", "put your hands on your knees." Performing such actions, the subject of silence passes into a state of humble contemplation, and the movement of hands down adds disappointment and fatigue to the state, for example:

"She sat down on a bench near the wall, lowered her hands, and was silent" (V. Rasputin. Farewell to Matera);

c) the verb combination "thrown his hands behind his head". The subject of silence also connects the hands and the head, but the hands are already at the back of the head, this posture characterizes the state of dreamy reflection, pleasant remembrance.

CONCLUSION

Non-verbal means of communication play an important role in the communication process. In a situation of silence, when the verbal part of communication is absent, the role of non-verbal means is greatly enhanced. To understand the meaning of silence, the researcher needs to take into account not only the psychological state of the communicants, their character, the degree of acquaintance with the addressee, their behavior and the national specifics of communication. The analysis of non-verbal discourse helps to reveal and explain the ambiguity of silence, in which the movements, postures, gestures and facial expressions of the communicants are described through the words of the author. In the process of analyzing the situation of silence, we identified an intonation marker, emotional state markers, and their concretizers: kinesic and proxemic somatics. Kinetic somatics are represented by reactions: eye contact, no eye contact, face, mouth, head movements, hands, posture. Kinetic somatic reactions expressed by verbs, verb forms and IVA combinations characterize situations of silence associated with contemplation and expectation. VA verbs represent

situations of anxiety, dissatisfaction, etc. Proxemic somatic reactions are limited to lokum. Reactions of “movement in the locum” are divided into 3 groups:

- 1) multiple actions that characterize the state of reflection;
- 2) actions associated with smoking represent a state of reflection and awkwardness of the communicants;
- 3) movements from top to bottom characterize situations of silence, when the communicant tries to calm down, tunes in to a conversation, feels awkward, humble, sympathetic or complicit.

Movements from the locum characterize the situation of silence, when the subject does not want to start a dialogue or completes it. All analyzed non-verbal means clarify, clarify the situation of silence, allow to differentiate and describe this phenomenon more clearly.

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